

The study of Personal Resources of Psychological Capital and Problem-Focused coping in the JD-R Model

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 02, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 03, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Psychological Capital, Problem-Focused Coping, Job Demands And Resources, Organizational Citizenship Behaviors</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6326099</p>	<p><i>This research investigated the positive effects of psychological capital (psycap) and problem-focused coping on job stress and organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB). By using the Job demands and resources model (JD-R model) and conservation of resources theory (COR), we propose that problem-focused coping act as a mediator in a way that it can offset the negative effects of job demands on job stress and will ensure participation of a person in organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB). Additionally, we propose that problem-focused coping can also act as a mediator between psycap and job stress in a way that adequate supply of psycap can induce positive thinking and application of problem-focused coping that can further help a person to eliminate job stress. We tested our hypotheses in a field study (N=391) conducted in higher education institutions of Pakistan. Our study confirmed that despite application of problem-focused coping teachers' half coped with stress and avoid participating in OCB. Additionally, problem-focused coping did not mediate the effect of psycap on job stress in suggested direction. Our study brought forth an interesting yet an unexpected finding in form of problem-focused coping as suppressor instead of a mediator</i></p>

Introduction

Modern organizations are confronted with issues such as organizational crises (Probst&Raisch, 2005), increasing workload and responsibilities (Schaufeli& Bakker, 2004), that often challenge them. Same as other organizations, educational institutions also put pressure on educators because of reforms, hardships, increasing standards and accountability they encounter (Cefai&Cayioni, 2014). Previous studies, pertinent to various countries worldwide, have acknowledged teaching as a stressful profession and teachers as its most susceptible victims (Clipa&Boghean, 2015; Onen&Ulusoy, 2015). Moreover, it is also reported that stress in teaching has become a global problem (Hong, 2010) which has become a leading cause behind teachers' attrition (Skaalvik&Skaalvik, 2011; Smithers& Robinson, 2008).

In the field of industrial psychology various job stress models have been established, however, studies on these models have been restricted to work characteristics that consequently undermines the value of a person's psychological capacities that can prove to be a significant determinant of adaptation to work environment (Xanthopoulou, et. al. 2007). Keeping in view, the dearth of literature, we gain insights from the conservation (COR- Hobfoll, 2002, 1989) and offer a framework for teachers' job stress that deals directly with their psycap and problem-focused coping at a time in the same model and in a way that can help teachers not only survive, but also flourish in their profession. Our model extends the JD-R model by introducing for the first-time problem-focused coping and psycap as potential resources that mobilize teachers' psychological capabilities that results in to decreased job stress and increased participation in desirable workplace behaviors such as organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB).

Theoretical Foundations of the Research

Keeping in view the central aim of our research that was to extend the JD-R model, we present the contextual framework of this research by discerning the nature of stress in the workplace with a positive lens. For that we use the theory underpinning the field of Positive psychology that restore the original mission of psychology, which is not being just the study of pathology, damage, and weakness but rather a study of virtue (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000).

Psycap has been defined as “an individual’s positive psychological state of development, and it is characterized by (1) having confidence (self-efficacy) to put necessary effort in to succeed at challenging tasks; (2) making a positive attribution (optimism) about succeeding now and in the future; (3) persevering toward goals and, when necessary, redirecting paths to goals (hope) in order to succeed; and (4) when beset by problems and adversity, sustaining and bouncing back and even beyond (resilience) to attain success” (Luthans, Youssef, et al., 2007).

The operational definition of Psycap manifests that its components, such as hope, efficacy, resilience and hope are set differently from the aspects of human capital (knowledge, skills, and abilities) and social capital (includes one’s network of relationships). Still, the common ground between Psycap and human and social capital remains that all of them are likely to develop (Luthans, Avey, & Patera, 2008). Likewise, problem-focused coping as devised by Lazarus (1998) is a positive way of coping wherein a person trusts his or her own capabilities to do something constructive to deal effectively with stress-inducing situations.

It is also good to mention here that the basic inspiration behind using Psycap and problem-focused coping as the positive personal capacities of a person stems from the Conservation of Resource theory (COR) offered by Hobfoll (1989). Our research is based on the two major assumptions of COR theory. Firstly, we ascertain that in order to deal effectively in any stress- provoking situation, individuals invest their resources that we introduced in the JD-R model in form of problem-focused coping and four personal resources, namely, self-efficacy, hope, optimism, and resilience, combined as a higher order construct known as psycap. Secondly, we also investigate problem-focused coping as a psychological resource of the teachers that they protect, save, and accumulate in order to generate other positive outcomes, such as increased participation in citizenship behaviors (Hobfoll, 2002, 1989).

Keeping in view the theoretical assumptions of our research, it is desirable to introduce here the Job Demands-Resources Model and the common ground it shares with the COR Theory. The JD-R Model (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004), is a stress framework that encapsulates a positive perspective to examine stress by considering the both health enhancing and the health impairment aspects of the workplace. Some former stress models like the Job Demands Control Model (Karasek, 1979) and the Effort Reward Imbalance Model (Siegrist, 1996) primarily focused on the negative aspects of work, such as a high workload and insufficient rewards that produce negative consequences in the form of ill health and psychological strain. Unlike the old stress models, the JD-R Model examines not only these negative aspects, but also the positive job characteristics and their effects on organizational outcomes. Further, the JD-R Model shares common ground with the COR theory, which provides theoretical foundations for our study. First, both the JD-R Model and COR theory assume that resources are significant determinants of threats/demands and negative outcomes. Second, the motivational process of JD-R Model explains the resource accumulation assumption of the COR theory for how resources are accumulated to produce other positive organizational outcomes.

In the light of the above discussion, it becomes evident that the application of the JD-R Model is in line with the contextual background of our study that tends to study job stress using a positive lens.

Theory and Hypotheses

Our research makes a salient contribution with inclusion of problem-focused coping in the JD-R Model. Despite the fact that coping has been defined differently by the researchers, however, according to Lazarus and Folkman’s (1984) individual’s coping depends on the cognitive appraisal of events and circumstances and the capability to cope in consequence to the individual’s transaction with the environment. They devised two broad sets of coping strategies, namely problem focused and emotion focused coping. Although these coping strategies may either be applied separately or simultaneously when encountering a demanding situation, contrasting the effectiveness of both types of coping, Violanti (1992) comprehended that a problem-focused coping produces more effective coping strategies for stress alleviation. This can be confirmed from the findings of the study by Tolbert (2007), who investigated the effectiveness of problem-focused and emotion-focused coping strategies of teachers for stress alleviation. The results of this study confirmed that those teachers who adopted emotion-focused, instead of problem-focused coping, they almost half coped with stress through anger which later on resulted in their poor health and poor well-being. Thus, the evidence suggests that problem- focused coping is likely to result in positive outcomes, such as low stress and better performance (Verešová & Malá, 2012) as its mainstay is on problem resolution and improving the situation by planning, taking action, and seeking information. Besides, the empirical evidences also suggest that those teachers who frequently use problem-focused coping not only experience less stress (Betoret, 2006) rather, they have increased feelings of participation, enjoyment and vigor (Parker & Martin, 2009).

Summing up, although the cognitive process of problem-focused coping may appear as a “hidden factor”, yet its role as a mediating variable (like appraisal and coping) cannot be denied during a potentially stressful situation. Provided

the scarcity of research while examining problem-focused coping as a mediator in the JD-R model, it would be useful and interesting to investigate its role as a mediator in the health impairment process of JD-R model when determining job stress in presence of high job demands. Thus, we formulate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1: Problem-focused coping will mediate the relationship between job demands and the job stress of teachers.

Consistent with the findings of Lazarus and Folkman (1984), psycap turns out to be a critical resource to cope with stressful events at work. In line with this view is the finding of Oginska-Bulik (2005) who stated that the reduction in demands of the job and an increase in personal resources, such as emotional intelligence, personal traits, and the psycap of a job holder, eventually bring about a decrease in job stress. A good deal of previous research also suggests that various components of psycap, e.g., hope (Snyder et al, 1991), optimism (Totterdell, Wood & Wall, 2006) and resilience (Ong, Bergeman, Bisconti & Wallace, 2006) account for some meaningful variations in the job stress that individuals experience if a person adopts problem focused coping. For example, in one of the studies it is found that resiliency influence a person to prefer problem-focused coping than emotion -focused coping strategies (Everall et al. 2006) because its mainstay is positive adaptation in the face of adversity. This also confirms that psycaptends to predict the type of coping strategy (problem-focused) that a person employs (Ding et al. 2015; Chen & Lim, 2012). Subsequently, the coping strategy impacts the extent to which a person experiences job stress (Zhang, 2011; Li & Lu 2008). This suggests that psycap is a distal variable that predicts job stress through proximal variables such as problem-focused coping. Hence, we argue that psycap more likely influence teachers to adopt problem-focused coping strategies and as a consequence they experience less job stress. For instance, an efficacious person will might search for an objective way of coping that will sufficiently deal with the demands of the job that they face. Thus, it is likely that they will adopt problem-focused coping as they carry a strong believe that even at the apex of a hardship, they are capable enough to do something constructive (Bandura,2000). Therefore, we formulate the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2: Problem- focused coping will mediate the relationship between psycap and the job stress of teachers.

The empirical research on JD-R model generally acknowledge that the adequate supply of job resources results in to various positive workplace outcomes including citizenship behaviors (Che Meh & Nasurdin, 2009). There is established empirical research pertinent to the effect of evaluations of teachers regarding their available job resources such as job control, supervisory support and feedback on OCB independent of any intervening variable (e.g., Klein, 2003). This draws our attention to spot one of the shortcomings pertaining to the literature on teachers' stress and coping that although it supplied bulk of information that what teachers find stressful and how do they cope with it, yet it failed to provide enough evidences that what happens after coping has occurred. Precisely, there is a paucity of some prominent studies that have investigated problem-focused coping from a developmental perspective. Indeed, there is a need to examine the construct of problem-focused coping from a lens of positivity that can be accounted for development of constructive behaviors at the workplace. Adhering, to this dearth of literature, we investigated if problem-focused coping can mitigate the negative effects of demands of the job on teachers' motivation to perform OCB. As mentioned earlier, it is hard to find a good deal of research that take in to account the effect of problem-focused coping on teachers' job demands and willingness to display OCB. Hence, in this vein, the existing literature guided that the person's experiences of stress depend on the appraisal of the job demands (Hurst & Eby, 2010). Moreover, as problem-focused coping seek positive ways to evaluate a potentially stressful situation, therefore it results in to more positive outcomes such as reduced stress, lower withdrawal intentions, higher performance and well-being (Subramanian and Kumar 2012; Brown et al. 2005; Hockey 1997). It seems plausible that if an employee will be able to evaluate their mandatory tasks at work by using problem-focused coping, they will be happy with their work environment and will show their willingness to engage in extra role behaviors such as OCB. Therefore, we offer following hypothesis that investigates problem-focused coping as a facilitator to engage teachers in performance of OCB despite high job demands.

Hypothesis 3: Problem-focused coping will mediate the relationship between job demands and the organizational citizenship behaviors of teachers.

Method

Participants and Procedure

Our research was carried out among faculty members employed in the higher education institutions of Pakistan that exist in form of six different clusters i.e. (Baluchistan, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab, Sindh, Federal Azad Jammu and Kashmir). Therefore, we used cluster sampling and with known size of population of total number of faculty members belonging to each cluster, a sample size of 391 respondents was determined according to the calculations of sample size formula (Yamane, 1967). The obtained sample of 391 respondents the criterion of sample size used for multiple regression analysis with more than 10 observations for each of the three scales for measuring the independent variables (Hair, Anderson, Tatham, & Black, 1995). Moreover, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test also confirmed the adequacy of the sample size of our research (Naidoo, 2011). Our study used survey design that adopted pre-established questionnaires that were pre-tested for establishing validity and reliability before putting in to the field (Meadows, 2003). Once the questionnaires were scrutinized for their validity and reliability and absence of common-method bias, they were administered personally to all the sampled universities. Questionnaires were delivered via email to those universities which were located in remote areas like Baluchistan, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, from where personal visits were beyond the researcher's resources. After the expiry of the response time period of seven days, a total of 388 questionnaires were returned out of 395 (including both personally administered and sent through email). Hence a response rate of 98.2% was secured in the end. Approximately 56% of respondents who participated in our research, were within the range of (25-35) years of age. Besides, 59% of the respondents were married and 62% of them were having a permanent nature of employment. Furthermore, majorities of respondents were M.Phil. (35%) and Masters (33%) who were serving their organizations as Lecturers (55%) and Assistant Professors (31%).

Measures

The population of our study comprised of teachers who follow English as medium of instruction, and can easily read and understand it, hence questionnaires were distributed in English. *Teachers' job demands questionnaire*: Teachers' potential job demands were extracted from an inventory by Fimian (1984). The instrument represents 29 arrays of events that act as sources of stress. The instrument had high face validity with all items scored directly in order to avoid potential problems associated with reverse-worded items (Boyle, 1979). All responses were scored on a five-point Likert type scale, with response options ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree" (with corresponding scores being 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 respectively). A high score of a certain item indicates a higher job demand.

Job Stress Questionnaire:

Teachers' job stress was measured with the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS; Cohen, Kamarck, & Mermelstein, 1983). For measuring psychological stress, PSS is considered as one of the accepted tools. PSS is a self-reported questionnaire, designed to gauge "the degree to which individuals appraise situations in their lives as stressful".

Problem-Focused Coping Questionnaire:

Brief COPE was utilized to tap teachers' responses (Carver, Scheier, & Weintraub, 1989). It is a self-report questionnaire which encapsulates and assesses various coping behaviors and thoughts a person may have in response to a stress provoking situation and is based on the COPE inventory (Carver, Scheier, & Weintraub, 1989) Sample items include "you have been taking action to try to make the situation better", "you have been getting help and advice from others".

Psycap Questionnaire:

Teachers' Psycap was measured with PCQ-12 (Luthans, Avolio, Avey & Norman, 2007) which is the shorter version of the original 24 item Psycap Questionnaire (PCQ- 24) (Luthans, Youssef et al., 2007). The reliability and validity of both shorter as well as long versions has already been established in previous researches such as (Avey, Avolio, & Luthans, 2011).

Job Resources Questionnaire:

Teachersperceived social support was measured by Caplan, Cobb, French, VanHarrison and Pinneau (1980) that includes four-item index for describing the extent to which respondent’s experienced social support from certain sources such as coworkers, supervisors, spouse, family/ spouse. Sample items included “How much people such as your co-worker, supervisor or family go out of their way to do things to make your work life easier for you?” This measure has remained one of the most established and widely adopted scales to measure social support in job with adequate internal consistency (Lim, 1996). Job controlwas measured by “control at work items” adapted from Frese, Kring, Soose&Zempel (1996). The scale’s subscale “control at work” correlated positively with self-efficacy, tendency of employees to overcome barriers, willingness of employees to take an active approach and proactivity.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior Questionnaire:

OCB was measured by employing William & Anderson’s (1991) scale. This scale includes 7 items for each OCB (Che Meh &Nasurdin, 2009).

Results & Discussions

For valid interpretations of the data, SEM requires data preparation and data screening (Kline, 2005). Therefore, descriptive analysis regarding missing data, sample size, outliers, normality, homoscedasticity, linearity and multi-co linearity was done. The data of our research surpassed all the initial diagnostics and was ready for SEM analysis.

Our model of the research was tested with structural equation modeling (SEM), using AMOS computer program (Arbuckle, 1997). The estimation method employed maximum likelihood and the overall fit of the model was tested by χ^2 Goodness -of- fit statistic (Joreskog et al., 1993). Nevertheless, χ^2 Goodness -of- fit statistic is sensitive to sample size, therefore comparative fit index (CFI; Bentler, 1990), Root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA; Browne and Cudeck, 1993) and Tucker Lewis index (TLI; Tucker and Lewis, 1973) were selected for assessing the fit of the models our research.In addition to the fit indices mentioned above the Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI; Mulaik et al., 1989) was also taken in to account for evaluating the relative parsimony of the nested first-order and second-order measurement models.

Specifically, an uncorrelated, first order model-1a, where work related demands, professional demands, discipline and professional investment were represented as independent constructs, was compared with a second order model 1-b. The Model-1b of the study comprised second-order factors of job demands (indicated by latent constructs of work-related demands, professional demands, discipline and professional investment). Results supported the latent constructs of job demands as one general latent factor, since the second-order CFA model fitted better the data. Likewise, the second-order CFA model 2b of pycap, 3b (indicated by latent constructs of job control, feedback and social support) and 4b (represented by latent factors of organizational citizenship behavior towards individuals and organization)fitted better the data than the first-order model 2a, 3a and 4a (c.f. Table 1). In addition to this (Model 5) and (Model 6) encompassed a single latent factor with 4 items each tapping the construct of job stress and problem-focused coping respectively.After theslight re- specification of the model, all constructs achieved acceptable. The re-specification of the model was done on the basis of low standardized factor loading (<0.50) (Hair et al. 2006) and large modification indices (≥ 4) (Dabholkar&Bagozzi, 2002).

Table 1
Goodness-of-fit statistics of first and second order CFA models

Model	χ^2	$\Delta \chi^2$	Df	ΔDf	CFI	TLI	RMSEA	PNFI
1a	122.327		48		.921	.892	.064	.639
2a	97.567		28		.948	.900	.081	.578
3a	43.385		13		.964	.941	.078	.588
4a	223.862		39		.854	.794	.111	.589
1b	173.135	-50.808 ($P < .001$)	51	3	.871	.833	.079	.641
2b	131.762	-34.195	30	2	.923	.874	.094	.603

		(<i>P</i> < .001)						
3b	43.385	0	13	0	.964	.941	.078	.588
4b	232.908	-9.046	40	1	.848	.907	.112	.599
		(<i>P</i> < .001)						
5	3.685		1		.952	.952	.084	.935
6	2.053		2		1.00	.999	.008	.331

Note. Model (1a, 2a, 3a, 4a, 5&6) = first-order measurement CFA model, Model (1b, 2b, 3b&4b) = second-order measurement CFA model

Table 2 demonstrates the items which were dropped from their respective scales due to low standardized factor loadings.

Table 2
Items dropped due to low standardized factor loadings

Construct	Items
Job demands	The pace of your work/job day is too fast The number of students in your class are too much
Job stress	There is too much administrative paperwork in your job How often you felt confident about your ability to handle your personal problems How often you felt that things were going your way
Job resources	When you look at your job as a whole, it allows you to make decisions Your manager or coworkers let you know how well you are doing on your job Your supervisor or coworkers on this job almost never give you any "feedback" about how well you are doing in your work
OCB	You take unscheduled work breaks You spend great deal of time on personal phone conversations You complain about insignificant things at work

Mediation Effects

The *causal step approach* introduced by Barron and Kenny (1986). Though popular, yet this approach has been criticized heavily on multiple grounds such as ineffective to quantify indirect effects (Hayes, 2009), lowest in power (Fritz & MacKinnon, 2007), and erroneous conclusion of mediation effect (Holmbeck, 2002). Considering the aforementioned limitations, a nonparametric technique to the estimation of effect size, bootstrapping was employed that draws the inference based on the estimate of the indirect effect itself (Hayes, 2009; Preacher and Hayes, 2004).

Results

Three pre-requisite conditions were examined before testing mediation that found job demands and psycap were significantly related to job stress. Likewise, Job demands and job resources were also the significant predictors of organizational citizenship behavior, job demands were significant predictor of problem-focused coping ($\gamma = 0.149$; $p = .007$), psycap significantly related to problem-focused coping ($\gamma = 0.616$; $p < .001$). Similarly, problem-focused coping established a significant relationship with job stress ($\gamma = -0.132$; $p = .031$) and with organizational citizenship behavior ($\gamma = 0.248$; $p = .002$). Thus, preliminary results allowed examining hypothesis 1, 2 & 3.

We followed the recommendations of (Holmbeck, 1997; Frazier, Tix, & Barron, 2004) for mediation analysis and therefore, a full mediation model Model-1a was set up with job demands indirectly related to job stress through problem-focused coping. Model-1a was compared with Model-1b, that was with an added path from job demands to job stress. The results made it quite evident that although the Model-1a had an unacceptable fit to the data, however, Model-1b significantly improved the fit of the data with addition of a direct path from job demands to job stress ($\Delta \chi^2(2) = 75.256$, $p < .001$, c.f. Table 3). Moreover, the values of CFI, TLI and RMSEA were also within the acceptable limits, suggesting that Model-1b yielded a better fit to the data than Model-1a. Besides model fit, the standardized path coefficients of Model-1b from job demands to problem-focused coping ($\gamma_{21} = 0.177$; $p = .001$), from problem-focused coping to job stress ($\gamma_{31} = -0.321$; $p < .05$) and from job demands to job stress ($\gamma_{11} = .630$; $p < .001$) were all significant and in the predicted direction (cf. Figure 1). Furthermore, addition of another direct path in the Model-1b from psycap to job stress for testing hypothesis 2 in Model-1C, did not result in better fit as presented in Table 3, $\Delta \chi^2(1) = 3$, (*N.S.*). The results of inspection of standardized direct

effect of independent variable on dependent variable although confirmed a significant positive effect of psycap on problem-focused coping ($\gamma_{42} = 0.300$; $p < .001$) but the standardized direct effect from problem-focused coping to job stress turned out to be insignificant ($\gamma_{31} = -0.085$; $p = .077$). These results lead to reject the hypothesis 4, suggesting that problem-focused coping did not mediate the direct relationship between psycap and job stress. Subsequently, in the Model-1d we removed the path from psycap to problem-focused coping and the fit of this model was re-examined. As mentioned in the Table 3 the removal of this path deteriorated the fit of the model-1d. However, when a direct path from job demands to OCB was added in Model- 1e, with the intention of testing hypothesis 3, it resulted in a significant improvement of model fit ($\Delta \chi^2(1) = 29.58$, $p < .001$, C.f. Table 3). Hence comparatively than Model- 1d, Model-1e stood the best model based on the model fit indices. Subsequently, the standardized path estimates of job demands to problem-focused coping ($\gamma_{12} = 0.309$; $p < .001$), from problem-focused coping to organizational citizenship behavior ($\gamma_{53} = 0.296$; $p < .001$) and from job demands to organizational citizenship behavior ($\gamma_{13} = -0.328$; $p < .001$) were all significant and in the expected direction (c.f. Figure 1).

Furthermore, the results of bootstrapping as mentioned in Table 4, demonstrates that problem-focused coping had a significant indirect effect on a direct path between job demands to job stress. However, the inspection of direct and indirect effects brought forth an unexpected, yet an interesting finding that the magnitude of effect of job demands on job stress slightly increased (from $\gamma = 0.591$ to $\gamma = 0.630$; $p < .001$). Moreover, indirect effect of job demands on job stress turned out opposite ($z = -.057$, $p = .002$) to the direct effect ($\gamma = 0.630$ $p < .001$) after inclusion of problem-focused coping as a mediator. These results lead to conclude that problem-focused coping caused inconsistent mediation (suppression) between the relationship of job demands and job stress (Hamilton, 1987). MacKinnon et al. (2000) defines a suppressor variable the one which increases the predictive validity of some other variable or set of variables when it is included in a regression equation. Similarly, the results of standardized path estimate of model-1e indicated that after inclusion of problem-focused coping as a mediator, the magnitude of the direct effect of job demands on OCB stood significant and increased from ($\gamma = -0.296$ to $\gamma = -0.328$; $p < .001$, c.f. Table 4), indicating a suppression effect. However, the opposite sign of indirect effect from job demands to organizational citizenship behavior ($z = .080$, $p < .01$, cf. Table 4) suggested that problem-focused coping instead of mediation caused suppression between direct effect of job demands on OCB (Rucker, Preacher, Tormala and Petty, 2011). Hence, it was concluded that individuals despite the utility of problem-focused coping stay away from citizenship behavior due to high job demands. Additionally, it was also noticeable that Model 1 (Mediation effects) shows different statistics of all the direct effects that were tested previously, without inclusion of mediators, for example the effect of job demands on job stress changed (from $\gamma = 0.591$ to $\gamma = 0.630$; $p < .001$), psycap to job stress (from $\gamma = -0.281$ to $\gamma = -0.21$; $p < .001$), job resources to OCB (from $\gamma = 0.363$ to $\gamma = 0.21$; $p < .001$) and job demands to OCB (from $\gamma = -0.266$ to $\gamma = -0.328$; $p < .001$). This difference in the absolute magnitude of the direct path coefficients (without sign change) is interpreted as the change in the strength of the influences conveyed through that pathway after the inclusion of problem-focused coping as a mediator in the model (McIntosh & Gonzalez-Lima, 1994).

Table 3
Comparison of Fit indices of Model 1, 2 & 3

Model	χ^2	$\Delta \chi^2$	<i>Df</i>	CFI	TLI	RMSEA
<i>Model 1a: Full mediation</i>						
(JS ← Cop ← JD, JS ← Cop ← PsyCap, OCB ← Cop ← JD, OCB ← JR)	527.398	-	126	.887	.863	.097
<i>Model 1b: Partial Mediation</i>						
(JS ← Cop ← JD, JS ← Cop ← PsyCap, JD ← Cop ← OCB, OCB ← JR, JS ← JD)	452.142	75.256 (<i>P</i> < .001).	124	.908	.886	.088
<i>Model 2c: Partial Mediation</i>						
(JS ← Cop ← JD, JS ← Cop ← PsyCap, JD ← Cop ← OCB, OCB ← JR, JD ← JS, JS ← PsyCap)	449.142	3 <i>Not significant.</i>	123	.908	.886	.088
<i>Model 2d: Partial Mediation</i>						
JS ← Cop ← JD, OCB ← Cop ← JD, OCB ← JR, JD ← JS, JS ← PsyCap	565.458	-116.316 (<i>Not significant</i>)	124	.876	.847	.102
<i>Model 2e: Partial Mediation</i>						
JS ← Cop ← JD, OCB ← Cop ← JD, OCB ← JR, JD ← JS, JS ← PsyCap, OCB ← JD	535.878	29.58 (<i>P</i> < .001)	123	.844	.855	.099

Table 4

Direct, indirect and total effects of problem-focused coping as a mediator between job demands and job stress

Visual depiction of parameter	Direct effect without mediator	Direct effect with Mediator, <i>P</i> = ≤0.05	Indirect effect, <i>P</i> = ≤0.05	Total effect, <i>P</i> = ≤0.05
JS ← Cop ← JD	0.591***	0.630**	-0.057*	0.573**
OCB ← Cop ← JD	-0.266***	-0.328**	0.080**	-0.248**

Figure 1 Standardized parameter estimates of Structural Equation Model-2

Discussions

Summing up the results of hypothesis 1, it is ascertained that teachers who exclusively rely on use of problem-focused coping to diminish the effect of their job demands on job stress are likely to suffer from fewer opportunities for recovery of lost energy during this process. As a result, despite using problem-focused coping they fail to completely eliminate the effect of their high job demands on the levels of stress they experience. This unexpected yet an interesting finding can be explained in a way that job demand is composed of an important physical component which drains much of the physical energy of a person resulting in the emergence of stress and emotional exhaustion, regardless of its interference with coping of any sort (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Problem-focused coping, certainly is a process that consumes psychological energy of a person, it is therefore unlikely for it to take in to account the physical component of job demands (Broeck, Vansteenkiste, De Witte & Lens 2008). In consequence to this, problem-focused coping might influence the psychological component but it fails to address the physical energetic component of job demands hence resulting in to job stress. Moreover, since problem-focused coping requires efforts and energies, hence, from the standpoint of its effectiveness to reduce stress the opportunities for replenishment are equally important (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). From the view point of COR theory distraction might foster replenishment of energy resources and can provide individuals with opportunities to interrupt resource loss spiral and instead create resource gain spiral (Llorens et al. 2007). Distraction refers to the engagement of a person in any alternate pleasurable activity that not only reduce stress but also enhance the effectiveness of problem-focused coping by providing a person an opportunity of rest and complete detachment from the stressful situation (Gaudreau & Blondin 2004). Thus, it becomes indispensable for the universities administration to look up for such distraction opportunities for the teachers as their absence would keep the psychobiological system of teachers activated thus leading to a state of sustained activation that will ultimately result in to extreme levels of job stress (Demerouti et al. 2005).

Previously, researchers mainly emphasized on job resources with a moderating potential in the prevention of exhaustion due to high job demands in the health impairment process of JD-R (Bakker et al., 2005). However, the findings of our research pertinent to hypothesis 3 suggested that problem-focused coping can play more active role not only in the health impairment but also in the motivational process of JD-R model. This assumption was based on the findings of the extended JD-R model by (Xanthopoulou, et.al. 2007) where personal resources of self-efficacy, optimism and self-esteem mediated the relationship between job resources and work engagement. In other words, the environmental factors and organizational outcomes have found to be related with each other via people's appraisal of their environment (the way people comprehend, formulate or react to their environment) either through mediation or through moderation effects. Nevertheless, our research brought an interesting finding that problem-focused coping as against to what was expected, proved to be a suppressor between job demands and citizenship behavior which implies that even after the application of problem-focused coping teachers restricted themselves from performing citizenship behavior at the workplace due to high job demands. A possible reason behind this finding can be that job demands exhaust much of the energy of a person which is why he/she finds less vigor to engage in OCB (Schaufeli, Bakker, & Salanova, 2006). This view can be further explained with the theory of stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984) which argues that a stress provoking situation stimulates the process of cognitive coping of a person that further influences their performance. This theory suggests that Problem-focused coping mode may drain much of the physical as well as psychological energy of a person which can further hinder their involvement in extra-role behaviors such as OCB (Broeck, Vansteenkiste, De Witte & Lens, 2008). Taken together, high job demands triggers a person's coping and it eventually depletes the energy of a person. This declining energy level induces a deficit in employee's expendable energy to such an extent that they choose to stay away from any extra-role behavior such as OCB.

Although the hypothesis 2 of our research proposed that problem-focused coping will mediate the direct effect of psycap on job stress, but the evidence is in contrast to what was expected. The results suggested that a direct path from psycap to job stress is not mediated by the problem-focused coping. This discrepancy between what was predicted and what was actually found can be explained in a way that the relationship between psycap and job stress may be described in terms of slightly different and complex mediation mechanism that might involves multiple sequential mediators (Krasikova., Lester & Harms, 2015). For example, it is possible that psychological health can be one such mediator that can influence the effect of psycap on person's coping and eventually job stress (e.g., Carver et al., 2010). Likewise interpersonal relationships along with problem-focused coping can also be another mediator which can influence the effect of psycap on job stress. Psycap can help a person to develop positive relationships at workplace which can help them to cope effectively with job stress (e.g. seeking advice on how to better cope with excessive job demands or discussing how to address the prevailing flaws of the organization) (Venkataramani, Green, & Schleicher, 2010).

Conclusion and Future Research Directions

Our research extended previous research on teachers' job stress by taking in to account their psychological capacities of psycap and problem-focused coping. Consequently, the JD-R model was extended with the inclusion of psycap and problem-focused coping. This was done to provide deeper understanding of teachers' cognitive appraisal process of job demands and job resources that can affect their behaviors in form of reduced job stress and high participation in OCB. Our research ended on a final note that the health impairment and motivational process of the JD-R model were supported by the inclusion of psycap and problem-focused coping. Thus, the proposed model of the present study brought in lime light a more balanced approach of employee well-being which suggests that a proper utility of psycap and problem-focused coping can restrict negative outcomes such as job stress and can ensure positive workplace behaviors such as OCB. We focused on the mediating role of problem-focused coping in the health impairment as well as the motivational process of JD-R model. In this regard our research found problem-focused coping as a suppressor between a direct relationship of job demands to job stress and from job demands to OCB. These results encourage the future research to examine the direct relationship between job demands with job stress and between job demands with OCB, more closely as there was a strong relationship between them which also increased even after controlling for problem-focused coping. Likewise, our research also focused on mediating role of problem-focused coping between psycap and job stress however the results did not favor the aforementioned relationship. It is recommended to the upcoming researchers that they can study the relationship between psycap and job stress from a slightly different perspective by adding multiple mediators along with problem-focused coping such as psychological health (e.g., Carver et al., 2010; Taylor et al., 2000) and interpersonal relationships (Venkataramani, Green, & Schleicher, 2010).

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